

1 Influence of soil texture on the estimation of soil organic carbon from 2 Sentinel-2 temporal mosaics at 34 European sites

3 Wetterlind, J.¹, Simmler, M.², Castaldi, F.³, Borůvka, L.⁴, Gabriel, J.L.⁵, Gomes, L.C.⁶, Khosravi, V.⁴, Kivrak, C.⁷,
4 Koparan, M.H.⁷, Lázaro-López, A.⁵, Łopatka, A.⁸, Liebisch, F.⁹, Rodriguez, J.A.⁵, Savaş, A.Ö.⁷, Stenberg, B.¹, Tunçay,
5 T.⁷, Vinci, I.¹⁰, Volungevičius, J.¹¹, Žydelis, R.¹¹, Vaudour, E.¹²

6

7 ¹ Swedish University of Agricultural Science (SLU), Department of Soil and Environment, Skara, Sweden

8 ² Agroscope, Sustainability Assessment and Agricultural Management, Ettenhausen, Switzerland

9 ³ National Research Council of Italy (CNR) Institute of BioEconomy, Firenze, Italy

10 ⁴ Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU), Faculty of Agrobiolgy, Food and Natural Resources,
11 Department of Soil Science and Soil Protection, Prague, Czech Republic

12 ⁵ Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (INIA-CSIC), Madrid, Spain

13 ⁶ Aarhus University (AU), Department of Agroecology, Tjele, Denmark

14 ⁷ Republic of Turkey Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, General Directorate of Agricultural Research and
15 Policies (TAGEM), Ankara, Türkiye

16 ⁸ Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation – National Research Institute (IUNG), Puławy, Poland;

17 ⁹ Agroscope, Agroecology and Environment, Zürich, Switzerland

18 ¹⁰ Environmental Protection Agency of the Veneto Region (ARPAV), Italy

19 ¹¹ Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry (LAMMC), Institute of Agriculture, Kėdainiai,
20 Lithuania

21 ¹² Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, AgroParisTech, UMR EcoSys, 91120 Palaiseau, France

22

23

24 Highlights

- 25 ● Sentinel-2-based study of how soil texture influences SOC prediction performance
- 26 ● Local models at 34 sites with a large range of pedo-climatic conditions across Europe
- 27 ● Large differences in prediction performance for SOC and clay content using satellite data
- 28 ● Evidence of the influence of soil texture on SOC prediction performance but weak and variable

29 **Abstract**

30 Multispectral imaging satellites such as Sentinel-2 are considered a possible tool to assist in the
31 mapping of soil organic carbon (SOC) using images of bare soil. However, the reported results are
32 variable. The measured reflectance of the soil surface is not only related to SOC but also to several
33 other environmental and edaphic factors. Soil texture is one such factor that strongly affects soil
34 reflectance. Depending on the spatial correlation with SOC, the influence of soil texture may improve
35 or hinder the estimation of SOC from spectral data. This study aimed to investigate these influences
36 using local models at 34 sites in different pedo-climatic zones across 10 European countries. The study
37 sites were individual agricultural fields or a few fields in close proximity. For each site, local models to
38 predict SOC and the clay particle size fraction were developed using the Sentinel-2 temporal mosaics
39 of bare soil images. Overall, predicting SOC and clay was difficult, and prediction performances with a
40 ratio of performance to deviation (RPD) > 1.5 were observed at 8 and 12 of the 34 sites for SOC and
41 clay, respectively. A general relationship between SOC prediction performance and the correlation of
42 SOC and clay in soil was evident but explained only a small part of the large variability we observed in
43 SOC prediction performance across the sites. Adding information on soil texture as additional
44 predictors improved SOC prediction on average, but the additional benefit varied strongly between
45 the sites. The average relative importance of the different Sentinel-2 bands in the SOC and clay models
46 indicated that spectral information in the red and far-red regions of the visible spectrum was more
47 important for SOC prediction than for clay prediction. The opposite was true for the region around
48 2200 nm, which was more important in the clay models.

49
50 **Keywords:** remote sensing, satellite, SOC, clay, soil moisture, time series, field scale

51
52

53

54

55 **Introduction**

56 Soil organic carbon (SOC) affects soil spectra in the visible region (Vis, 350–750 nm) by absorption of
57 energy through excitation of electrons, and in the near infrared (NIR, 750–1100 nm) and short wave
58 infrared (SWIR, 1100–2500 nm) through overtones and combinations of fundamental vibrations in the
59 mid-infrared region (Stenberg *et al.*, 2010). This has been successfully used for predicting SOC content
60 under laboratory conditions with high spectral resolution instruments (e.g. Viscarra-Rossel *et al.*, 2006;
61 Nocita *et al.*, 2013; Barthès and Chotte, 2021). Encouraging performances have also been obtained
62 using field hyperspectral measurements (Gras *et al.*, 2014; Wetterlind *et al.*, 2015; Piccini *et al.*, 2024),
63 airborne and satellite hyperspectral images (Angelopoulou *et al.*, 2019; Mzid *et al.*, 2022), and
64 multispectral satellite data on a local scale (e.g. Gholizadeh *et al.*, 2018) or on a regional scale (Vaudour
65 *et al.*, 2019; Dvorakova *et al.*, 2020; Urbina-Salazar *et al.*, 2021).

66 Satellite remote sensing is frequently suggested as a possible tool for estimating and
67 monitoring soil properties and soil health indicators on a large scale (Smith *et al.*, 2020; Soubry *et al.*,
68 2021; Pandey & Pandey, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2023). The launch of the Sentinel-2 multispectral imaging
69 satellites Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-2B in 2015 and 2017, respectively, brought an increased interest
70 in using Earth observations to retrieve soil information, especially on SOC (Castaldi 2021; Vaudour *et*
71 *al.*, 2022; Yuzugullu *et al.*, 2024). The spatial resolution of 10–20 m (10 of the 13 bands) makes the
72 Sentinel-2 satellites relevant for applications guiding soil and crop management at the field and farm
73 scale, and the short revisiting time of five days, or even less in areas with overlapping orbits further
74 away from the Equator, increases the availability of images with bare soil conditions for gathering soil
75 information.

76 However, the results of SOC prediction from satellite data are variable (Vaudour *et al.*, 2022).
77 Soil property mapping from satellite images is based on the interaction between sunlight and soil
78 surfaces as detected by satellite-borne sensors. Many factors affect the reflectance received by the

79 satellite sensors, including soil surface conditions (e.g. surface roughness, crop residues, and emerging
80 plants), soil moisture, soil type, and soil texture. In this regard, satellite imagery with a short revisit
81 time offers the possibility of collecting many bare soil images within a given time period. However, for
82 satellite imagery with medium (10–30 m) or coarser spatial resolution, pure bare soil pixels are difficult
83 to obtain. Therefore, over the last few years, some studies have focused on the influence of vegetation,
84 either green (Bartholomeus *et al.*, 2011; Ouerghemmi *et al.*, 2016) or dry (Castaldi *et al.*, 2019), to
85 describe the decrease in performance due to vegetation coverage and provide spectral index
86 thresholds for removing these effects. In addition to the vegetation index Normalised Difference
87 Vegetation Index (NDVI), which is used to discard green vegetated pixels (e.g. Demattê *et al.*, 2018;
88 Loiseau *et al.*, 2019), a now commonly used approach for removing the effect of dry vegetation consists
89 of thresholding with the Normalised Burn Ratio 2 (NBR2) spectral index (Castaldi *et al.*, 2019;
90 Dvorakova *et al.*, 2020). The effect of soil moisture on SOC prediction performance has mainly been
91 studied using laboratory spectroscopy (Minasny *et al.*, 2011; Nocita *et al.* 2013; Knadel *et al.*, 2022,
92 Metzger *et al.*, 2024) or synthetic satellite spectra simulated from laboratory spectroradiometric
93 measurements (Castaldi *et al.*, 2015). More recently, radar-derived soil moisture information has also
94 been considered (Urbina-Salazar *et al.*, 2021; Urbina-Salazar *et al.*, 2023; Zayani *et al.*, 2023). Another
95 approach reduces the varying effects of soil surface and retrieves a representative value of soil surface
96 condition consisting of considering a pixelwise median reflectance value over several years, instead of
97 single-date information. This temporal mosaicking also allows the extension of the mappable bare soil
98 area (Castaldi, 2021; Dvorakova *et al.*, 2021; Vaudour *et al.*, 2021; Heiden *et al.*, 2022; Žížala *et al.*,
99 2022; Urbina-Salazar *et al.*, 2023).

100 Although soil texture is sometimes mentioned as a possible reason for deviations in SOC
101 prediction results by Vis-NIR-SWIR spectroscopy (Stenberg, 2010; Wight *et al.*, 2016; Ogen *et al.*, 2018),
102 only a few studies have focused on disentangling the influence of soil texture on SOC prediction
103 performance using satellite data (Khosravi *et al.*, 2024). Therefore, the overall aim of this study was to
104 better understand the spectral information used for modelling SOC from satellite data, focusing on the

105 influence of soil texture. The study analyses the specific influence of texture on satellite-based SOC
106 prediction instead of targeting the overall improvement of SOC prediction from texture, as achieved
107 by Khosravi *et al.* (2024), with texture-based stratification of SOC models.

108 Particle size distribution, especially the clay fraction, strongly affects soil reflectance through
109 clay minerals and the iron (hydr)oxide minerals contained in the clay fraction. Clay minerals absorb
110 light at specific wavelengths, but the wavelength regions that hold information on clay minerals and
111 organic molecules are located close together in the spectra and sometimes overlap (Stenberg *et al.*,
112 2010; Wight *et al.*, 2016; Ogen *et al.*, 2018), with the risk of masking important information. This could
113 be especially problematic when using low spectral resolution multispectral data, such as from the
114 Sentinel mission. Soil texture also affects the visibility of SOC, with lower visibility of SOC in clayey soils,
115 where SOC can be hidden in soil aggregates (Balesdent *et al.*, 2000). Accordingly, Stenberg (2010)
116 found SOC overpredicted for sandy soils in a Swedish dataset. This was interpreted as an effect of the
117 smaller specific surface area in sandy soil and, therefore, a higher concentration of organic matter on
118 the exposed mineral particle surfaces. However, one of the strongest influences of soil texture related
119 to reflectance in satellite data is probably its influence on soil moisture (Bousbih *et al.*, 2019). Both
120 organic matter and clay content increase soil water-holding capacity and soil moisture (Manns *et al.*,
121 2016; Soltani *et al.*, 2019). Water largely influences soil reflectance through strong absorbance at
122 specific wavelengths (Bablet *et al.*, 2018; Soltani *et al.*, 2019). However, these regions are not included
123 in the multispectral bands registered by the satellites due to interference with water in the
124 atmosphere, so the main effect is in the darkening of the soil with increased soil moisture.

125 The influence of soil texture on the possibility of predicting SOC using multispectral satellite
126 data could be expected to be both favourable and unfavourable, depending on the nature of the
127 relationship between SOC and soil texture. If both soil properties follow the same (or the opposite)
128 spatial pattern, the combined effect on soil reflectance might help in modelling SOC. However, models
129 relying on a relationship between SOC and soil texture might not generalise well over larger areas, as
130 the SOC-to-soil texture relationship might change, and it will be difficult to detect changes in SOC

131 content over time that are not correlated to soil texture. If, on the other hand, the variation in SOC
132 does not follow the variability in soil texture, variability related to soil texture might hide a more subtle
133 variation in SOC, causing difficulties in predicting SOC.

134 The goal of this study was to investigate the influence of soil texture on SOC predictions using
135 Sentinel-2 temporal mosaics. The study therefore analysed how local within-site variability and
136 correlations in SOC and soil texture influence the possibility of predicting SOC from satellite data using
137 local models at sites in different pedo-climatic zones across Europe. Analyses of 34 individual sites in
138 10 European countries were carried out within the framework of the STEROPES project of the
139 European Joint H2020 Programme, EJP SOIL. The study focused on the field and farm scale, developing
140 site-specific models to further understand the basis for SOC models using satellite data and the role of
141 soil texture in explaining variations in SOC modelling results. The field or farm scale has the advantage
142 of reducing differences in management within the study sites, which might otherwise interfere with
143 the interpretations. Whereas most previous studies aimed at predicting SOC typically considered a
144 more reduced set of agropedological contexts and, most of the time, one study area within one
145 country, this study relied on an unprecedented set of local-scale study areas from across Europe.

146 The study aimed to answer four specific questions related to the influence of soil texture on
147 the estimation of soil organic carbon using Sentinel-2 temporal mosaics: (1) Does a stronger correlation
148 between SOC and soil texture favour better SOC prediction performance? (2) Does the variation and
149 overall amount of clay content affect SOC prediction performance? (3) Does adding information on soil
150 texture as additional predictors to the models improve SOC predictions? and (4) Are different spectral
151 bands important for predicting SOC compared with predicting clay?

152

153 **Materials and methods**

154 ***Study sites and soil datasets***

155 To investigate the influence of soil texture on SOC models using satellite data, soil samples and satellite
156 data were collected from 34 agricultural sites in 10 European countries covering different pedoclimatic
157 conditions and cropping systems (Figure 1, Supplementary Table S1) by decreasing latitude from
158 Sweden, Denmark, Lithuania, Poland, Czech Republic, France, Switzerland, Italy, Türkiye, and Spain.
159 The study sites were not selected to represent specific conditions but rather to serve as a variable
160 sample of possible conditions to increase the external validity of the findings. The sites covered a range
161 of soil types, from Cambisols and Luvisols of the temperate Atlantic central and continental regions
162 and Chernozems, Phaeozems, Histosols, Gleysols, and Arenosols in the Atlantic north and Nemoral
163 regions to Vertisols, Fluvisols, Calcisols, and Gypsisols in the Anatolian and Mediterranean regions.

164 The sites were individual or neighbouring fields ranging from a few hectares to more than 450
165 ha at two sites, with a median size of 17 ha (Supplementary Table S2). Soil samples were taken from
166 0–20 cm soil depths at all sites, except for the Italian sites, which were sampled at 0–30 cm, and the
167 French and Spanish sites, which were sampled at 0–10 cm. The sampled area at each sampling point
168 varied from 0.25 m² to 80 m². About half of the sites used a target sampling design based on soil maps
169 and/or satellite data, and the other half used a regular grid. The sampling design and methodology
170 were usually the same for sites within the same country. The number of samples and sample density,
171 however, also varied between individual sites from the same country, ranging from 16 to 280 samples
172 per site and 0.2 to 60 samples ha⁻¹. The median number of samples per site was 54, and the median
173 sample density was 3 samples ha⁻¹. The soil sampling dates also varied between the sites. Nine sites
174 from Sweden and Denmark were sampled before 2015, with the oldest sampling from 1992 at one of
175 the Danish sites. Most of the sites were sampled between 2018 and 2022. SOC contents and soil
176 texture (clay, silt, and sand particle size fractions) of the soil samples were determined using the
177 methods listed in Supplementary Table S3. The silt-sand particle size limit was 50 µm in all countries,

178 except Sweden, Lithuania, and Spain, where the limit was 63 μm . For these countries, soil texture data
179 were therefore converted to values that corresponded to a silt-sand limit of 50 μm using a log-linear
180 interpolation (see, e.g. Nemes *et al.* 1999).

181
182 *Figure 1.* Map showing the location of the 34 sites included in the study and the environmental stratification of
183 Europe (Metzger *et al.*, 2005).

184 **Satellite data**

185 A pixelwise temporal mosaicking approach was applied to select bare soil images using Sentinel-2
186 image collections and to obtain composite bare soil layers for each region of interest (Castaldi *et al.*,
187 2023) from the time series 2019–2022. The mosaicking approach was implemented by using the rgee
188 R package (Aybar *et al.*, 2020) to wrap the Earth Engine Python API for working in the Google Earth
189 Engine environment (Gorelick *et al.*, 2017) from within R (R Core Team, 2024). Google Earth Engine is
190 a cloud-based platform that was used here to gain access to Copernicus Sentinel-2 Multispectral
191 Instrument (MSI) level 2A dataset provided by the European Space Agency (ESA).

192

193 The approach consisted of two steps. In the first step, three filters were applied for each pixel and
194 acquisition date (Figure 2) to identify and select bare soil pixels.

195 I. **Atmospheric filter.** This includes a cloud filter to remove dates affected by clouds and cloud
196 shadows. The cs quality band from the combination of Cloud Score+ and the S2_HARMONIZED

197 dataset was used with a cs threshold of 0.7 to remove thin clouds, haze, and cirrus shadows.
198 The cs value is the similarity between the observed pixel and the theoretical clear reference

199 pixel based on their spectral distance. A snow mask was also applied using the MSK_SNOWPRB
200 quality band provided by ESA, removing records with > 10% probability of snow on the ground.

201 II. **Green vegetation filter.** The NDVI was calculated from bands 4 and 8 as follows: $(B8-$
202 $B4)/(B8+B4)$ was computed and pixels with $NDVI > 0.35$ were filtered out because they were

203 likely affected by green vegetation.

204 III. **Dry vegetation + soil moisture filter.** The NBR2 index was calculated from bands 11 and 12 as
205 $(B11-B12)/B11+B12$ and pixels having $NBR2 > 0.125$ (Castaldi *et al.*, 2019) were filtered out

206 because they were likely affected by dry vegetation and/or by high soil moisture content.

207

Pixelwise temporal mosaicking

208

209 Figure 2. General flowchart of the two temporal mosaicking approaches (adapted from Castaldi *et al.*, 2023). SM

210 indicates soil moisture.

211

212 In the second step, if at least three bare soil dates were left after applying the filters for each pixel, the
213 available data were combined using two mosaicking approaches to return bare soil composite images
214 (temporal mosaics):

215 A. The first approach involves selecting the **median** (50th percentile) reflectance values for each
216 band and pixel of the time series, with the aim of obtaining spectral data representative of the
217 average bare soil conditions not affected by extreme reflectance values.

218 B. The second approach, called **R90**, involves selecting the 90th percentile of reflectance values
219 of the time series for each band and pixel, with the aim of selecting dry conditions, assuming
220 that higher reflectance corresponds to lower soil moisture content. Using the 90th percentile
221 instead of the highest reflectance aims at excluding anomalously high reflectance values that
222 could arise, for example, when cloud masking fails (Castaldi *et al.*, 2023).

223 The outcome of these two mosaicking approaches was two composite bare soil layers of 10 m
224 resolution for each study site. The layers include reflectance information of the following bands of the
225 MSI instrument (central wavelength): B2 (492 nm), B3 (559 nm), B4 (664 nm), B5 (704 nm), B6 (740
226 nm), B7 (782 nm), B8 (842 nm), B8A (865 nm), B11 (1613 nm), and B12 (2202 nm; Sentinel-2 User
227 Handbook, 2015). Bands with a 20-m resolution (B5, B6, B7, B8A, B11, and B12) were resampled to 10
228 m. These layers were used to extract spectral data from soil sampling locations and then to develop
229 soil property prediction models.

230 ***Model development and validation***

231 Local models for predicting SOC or clay content were developed for each site using partial least squares
232 regression (PLSR) and random forest algorithms, as implemented in the Python machine learning
233 framework scikit-learn v. 1.3.0 (Pedregosa *et al.*, 2011). Predictors included the Sentinel-2 bare soil
234 spectral information processed as described in the previous section (10 bands; median or R90) and/or,
235 to predict SOC, information on the measured soil texture. Soil texture information from the soil
236 samples was included either as the clay fraction or as information on all three particle size fractions

237 (clay, silt, and sand). In the latter case, the three fractions were subjected to additive log ratio
238 transformation to the two log ratios $\log(\text{clay}/\text{sand})$ and $\log(\text{silt}/\text{sand})$. This transformation accounts for
239 the compositional nature of the data (e.g. Filzmoser *et al.*, 2018). Soil texture information was added
240 as a predictor in the SOC prediction models to study the influence of soil texture on SOC prediction
241 performance.

242 The optimal number of components to keep in the PLSR models was tuned based on the
243 minimum root mean squared error (RMSE) in leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO-CV). Random forest
244 models were fitted with default values for all hyperparameters apart from the number of trees, which
245 was set to 200 (no hyperparameter tuning was applied). Model performance was evaluated in LOO-CV
246 using the RMSE, the ratio of performance to deviation (RPD = $SD/RMSE$), the ratio of performance to
247 interquartile distance (RPIQ = $IQR/RMSE$), and Lin's concordance correlation coefficient (ccc). See
248 Appendix 3 of Piikki *et al.* (2021) for the definition and interpretation of these metrics. As a simple
249 baseline, we fitted 'dummy models' that always predict the mean of the target variable in the training
250 data, that is, the mean of the actual measured SOC or clay content in the training data. These baseline
251 models thus predict a constant value (calculated during model fitting) and use no predictors. The
252 performance of these dummy models was evaluated using the same LOO-CV procedure and metrics
253 as for the real models. To investigate the importance of the predictors, we calculated SHAP (SHapley
254 Additive exPlanations) values using the Python package SHAP (Lundberg & Lee, 2017). The importance
255 of each predictor was calculated as the mean absolute SHAP value. Across predictors, these were
256 normalised to sum to 100% to provide a measure of relative importance.

257 **Results**

258 ***SOC and texture data***

259 Across all sites, SOC content ranged from 0.2% to 12%. The highest SOC levels (above 7.5%) and the
260 largest range (> 6%) were recorded at two Danish sites (DNK 2 and 3) and one Swedish site (SWE 1;

261 Figure 3A). Apart from these sites, large ranges in SOC content (> 2%) were also found at four of the
262 other Swedish sites, and at one Czech (CZE 1), one Lithuanian (LTU 3), and one Swiss (CHE 4) site. The
263 lowest average SOC contents were found in Spain, at a site in Italy (ITA 4), at a Turkish site (TUR 2), and
264 at the Polish site (POL 1), not exceeding 1%, which has been established as a critical level below which
265 serious decline in soil quality might occur (desertification; Loveland & Webb, 2003). Most other sites
266 had average SOC content between 1% and 2%. Mainly, except for two Swiss sites (CHE 3 and 4), average
267 SOC content tended to be lower in the southern countries. An opposite tendency was observed in clay
268 content, except for the Swedish sites (Figure 3B). Across all sites, clay content ranged from 0.1% to
269 67%. In general, the Swedish and Turkish sites had the largest values and the largest ranges of clay
270 content. The average clay content ranged from 2% (Polish site, POL 1) to 40% (one of the Italian sites,
271 ITA 5). Average contents > 30% were found in some Italian, Spanish, Turkish, and Swiss sites. The range
272 in clay content tended to asymptotically increase with the area of the sites (log-linear Pearson, $r = 0.72$,
273 $p < 0.001$), while there was no statistical support for a similar relationship for the range in SOC ($r =$
274 0.05 , $p = 0.78$). Texture classes across the 34 sites were quite varied and covered the entire texture
275 triangle (Figure 3C), from coarse (such as the Danish sites) to fine (some Italian, Turkish, and Swedish
276 sites). Silt contents across all sites ranged from 3% to 76%. The highest average contents (62% and
277 64%) were found at a Czech (CZE 2) and a French site (FRA 1). Across all sites, sand content ranged
278 from 4% to 94%. The highest average sand content was above 70% for Danish and Polish sites. SOC
279 content showed positive correlations with clay content at 16 of the 34 sites, and negative correlations
280 at 5 of 34 sites (Figure 3D). Interestingly, all sites with negative correlations were from the
281 northernmost countries of Lithuania and Sweden.

282

283 **Figure 3.** SOC and texture analyses. **A)** Boxplots showing SOC content in the soil samples at each site. **B)** Boxplots
 284 showing clay content in the soil samples at each site. Boxplots with lower and upper hinges representing 25th
 285 and 75th percentiles, line in between representing median, and whiskers extending to 1.5 * IQR from both hinges.
 286 Jittered points represent individual sampling points. For SWE 1, DNK 2, and DNK 3, a few points fall outside the
 287 range shown for SOC and are not visible. **C)** Texture triangle showing individual sampling points coloured
 288 according to country. Texture classification is as used in the database of Hydraulic Properties of European Soils

289 (HYPRES, Wösten *et al.*, 1999). **D)** Correlation between SOC and clay content per site. White text indicates a
290 significant correlation (Pearson) at the 0.05 level.

291 ***Satellite data***

292 The average number of bare soil images available per soil sampling point at the individual sites varied
293 from 4 to 74 (Figure 4A). Two Italian sites stood out, with on average more than 70 bare soil images
294 per point, and three Swedish, the Spanish, and one Turkish site had more than 30 images on average
295 per point. However, the average number of bare soil images was below 20 for most of the sites. The
296 minimum number of bare soil images for a sampling point of 3 images was observed for 22 points,
297 mainly in Turkey, Denmark, Lithuania, and Poland. The similar clustering in the texture triangle in
298 Figure 3C as in the PCA score plots of the satellite data in Figure 4B and 4C indicates an influence of
299 soil texture on the satellite data. However, sites close in geography also tended to be close in the PCA
300 score plot, suggesting influences of factors acting on a larger scale related to more general differences
301 between the sites.

302 The PCA score plots in Figure 4B and 4C for median and R90 satellite data show very similar
303 patterns (median and R90 temporal mosaics from three sites as an example are shown in Figure S1).
304 However, at sites in two countries, Sweden and, to a lesser extent, Lithuania, using R90 resulted in
305 several anomalously high reflectance values (resulting in the outliers in the inset in Figure 4C). Further
306 inspection of the spectral data at these sampling points suggested that satellite images were affected
307 by thin clouds that were not detected by the cloud mask. We thus excluded four sites (SWE 3, 4, and
308 5, and LTU 3) from further analyses using the R90 method.

309 ***SOC and clay predictions using satellite data***

310 The performance of prediction models for both SOC and clay content varied largely between the sites
311 and was poor in many cases (Table 1 and Figure 5 for PLSR, Table S4 and Figure S2 for random forest).
312 Overall, PLSR models performed comparably with random forest models. As comparing the algorithms
313 is not the aim of this study, we henceforth focus on the results of the PLSR models.

314
 315 **Figure 4.** Satellite data. **A)** Boxplot showing the number of available bare soil images per soil sampling point after
 316 applying the cloud and vegetation filters in the time series from 2019 to 2022. Boxplots with lower and upper
 317 hinges representing 25th and 75th percentiles, line in between representing median, and whiskers extending to
 318 1.5 * IQR from both hinges. Jittered points represent individual sampling points. **B)** Principal component analysis
 319 (PCA) of the median satellite data. **C)** PCA of the R90 satellite data with (small inset) and without sites SWE 3,
 320 SWE 4, SWE 5, and LTU 3 (for these sites, the cloud filtering failed). Score plots representing the information in
 321 the first two principal components (PCs). The percentage of total variance in the data (10 satellite bands)
 322 explained by the PCs is given in parentheses. Each point in the score plot represents a sampling point.

323
 324 For each site and target variable (SOC or clay), we selected either the median or R90 satellite data as
 325 predictors, depending on, which resulted in a model with a smaller RMSE. On average, across the 34
 326 sites, there was no statistical support for a difference in prediction performance (RPD) for predicting
 327 SOC using satellite data compared to predicting clay using satellite data (Wilcoxon, $p = 0.39$; paired
 328 Wilcoxon, $p = 0.56$). The differences between the clay and SOC prediction performances varied greatly
 329 between the sites, with clay easier to predict at some sites and SOC on others. Clay content could be

330 predicted with RPD values > 1.5 at 12 of the 34 sites, and at 5 of those sites, the RPD was > 2.0 . At 10
 331 sites (29%), the models had RPD values < 1.1 , which was only slightly better than the RPD of close to,
 332 or just below 1.0 of the dummy models, which are simple baseline models that always predict the
 333 mean of the measured value in the training data (see methods). SOC content could be predicted with
 334 an RPD > 1.5 at 8 sites, and with an RPD > 2.0 at 2 sites. For SOC predictions, 8 sites (24%) had RPD
 335 values of < 1.1 . At 10 sites, the models had RPIQ values > 1.7 for both SOC and clay.

336
 337 **Figure 5. A)** Performance of site-specific PLSR models for predicting SOC using satellite data. **B)** Performance of
 338 site-specific PLSR models for predicting clay using satellite data. RPD and ccc were determined in leave-one-out
 339 cross-validation. The results are shown for the best models (smallest RMSE) using either the median or R90
 340 satellite data (corresponding to Table 1). The dotted lines indicate the performance of the dummy models, which
 341 are simple baseline models, always predicting the mean of the measured SOC or clay content in the training data
 342 (ignoring the satellite information). The solid lines are only eye guides. The order of sites (x-axis) corresponds to
 343 Figures 3A, 3B, and 4A.

344 *Table 1.* Performance of site-specific PLSR models for predicting SOC and clay as determined in leave-one-out cross-validation. Predictors in the models for SOC include satellite data only,
345 satellite data and texture information, or texture information only. The best models (smallest RMSE) using either the median or R90 satellite data, as well as using either clay only or
346 information on all three granulometric fractions (clay, silt, sand; 'allTex') are listed.

Site	SOC predictions												Clay predictions								
	Satellite				Satellite + texture				Texture				Satellite								
	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	Ccc	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	ccc	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	ccc	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	Ccc					
SWE 1	med	0.64	1.66	1.12	0.78	med	clay	0.65	1.65	1.12	0.78	allTex	1.04	1.02	0.69	0.14	med	3.43	1.54	2.33	0.75
SWE 2	r90	0.47	0.97	1.35	-0.05	med	clay	0.43	1.05	1.47	0.29	clay	0.42	1.10	1.53	0.34	med	3.02	1.19	1.65	0.55
SWE 3	med	0.27	0.97	1.08	0.09	med	clay	0.27	0.98	1.09	0.13	clay	0.26	1.02	1.13	0.15	med	4.67	2.95	5.46	0.94
SWE 4	med	0.30	1.29	1.72	0.58	med	allTex	0.27	1.43	1.91	0.69	clay	0.38	1.02	1.36	0.10	med	5.83	1.84	2.74	0.83
SWE 5	med	0.49	1.13	1.28	0.42	med	clay	0.33	1.69	1.90	0.79	clay	0.40	1.37	1.54	0.64	med	3.25	2.14	1.15	0.88
SWE 6	med	0.34	1.58	1.89	0.76	med	clay	0.34	1.58	1.90	0.76	clay	0.46	1.15	1.38	0.40	r90	4.61	1.42	1.41	0.70
DNK 1	med	0.08	1.45	1.83	0.71	med	clay	0.07	1.51	1.90	0.73	clay	0.12	0.96	1.21	-0.05	med	0.94	1.44	2.49	0.72
DNK 2	med	1.15	1.50	0.20	0.72	med	allTex	1.03	1.68	0.23	0.79	allTex	1.71	1.00	0.14	0.05	med	1.30	1.33	2.07	0.62
DNK 3	r90	1.01	1.61	1.48	0.77	p90	clay	1.03	1.59	1.46	0.76	allTex	1.44	1.13	1.04	0.43	med	1.64	1.04	1.15	0.21
DNK 4	r90	0.11	1.18	1.63	0.50	p90	allTex	0.10	1.29	1.78	0.60	allTex	0.12	1.06	1.46	0.26	med	1.43	0.97	1.02	0.04
DNK 5	med	0.18	1.15	1.52	0.42	p90	allTex	0.17	1.24	1.64	0.56	allTex	0.21	1.01	1.34	0.11	med	0.28	1.44	1.86	0.70
LTU 1	med	0.19	1.24	1.65	0.58	med	allTex	0.16	1.48	1.98	0.72	allTex	0.17	1.34	1.78	0.62	med	2.02	1.08	1.64	0.45
LTU 2	med	0.21	0.99	1.21	0.04	med	allTex	0.20	0.99	1.22	0.20	allTex	0.20	1.01	1.24	0.16	med	2.17	0.96	1.04	0.19
LTU 3	med	0.42	1.17	1.04	0.49	med	allTex	0.36	1.35	1.19	0.64	allTex	0.37	1.31	1.16	0.60	med	2.71	1.06	1.59	0.26
LTU 4	med	0.24	1.00	1.26	0.06	med	clay	0.20	1.18	1.48	0.48	clay	0.20	1.19	1.50	0.47	med	3.23	1.06	1.75	0.35
POL 1	med	0.21	1.44	1.33	0.74	med	clay	0.19	1.61	1.48	0.79	clay	0.20	1.52	1.41	0.74	med	1.73	1.19	1.07	0.58
CZE 1	med	0.39	1.06	0.97	0.24	med	clay	0.39	1.06	0.97	0.24	allTex	0.42	0.98	0.90	-0.03	r90	4.05	0.99	1.39	0.04
CZE 2	med	0.17	1.34	1.70	0.63	med	allTex	0.17	1.39	1.77	0.67	allTex	0.21	1.11	1.41	0.37	med	2.05	2.30	2.77	0.90
CZE 3	med	0.16	1.23	1.85	0.56	med	allTex	0.16	1.22	1.85	0.56	allTex	0.20	1.00	1.52	0.09	med	3.51	1.19	0.91	0.49
CZE 4	r90	0.27	1.10	1.21	0.37	p90	clay	0.27	1.10	1.21	0.36	allTex	0.30	0.99	1.09	0.00	med	3.68	1.00	1.09	0.26
FRA 1	r90	0.22	1.51	1.84	0.74	p90	clay	0.22	1.51	1.84	0.75	clay	0.25	1.31	1.59	0.61	med	1.74	2.34	4.50	0.90
CHE 1	r90	0.10	1.44	2.42	0.73	p90	clay	0.10	1.55	2.59	0.78	clay	0.11	1.42	2.38	0.69	r90	2.36	1.36	2.24	0.68
CHE 2	med	0.07	2.15	2.92	0.88	p90	clay	0.06	2.68	3.64	0.93	clay	0.10	1.61	2.19	0.78	med	2.31	1.43	1.90	0.75
CHE 3	med	0.24	1.10	1.58	0.39	med	allTex	0.24	1.11	1.59	0.40	allTex	0.24	1.13	1.63	0.43	med	2.86	1.01	1.19	0.24
CHE 4	r90	0.19	3.17	2.07	0.95	p90	clay	0.21	2.80	1.83	0.94	clay	0.39	1.54	1.00	0.75	med	2.82	1.79	2.27	0.83
CHE 5	r90	0.21	1.89	1.13	0.83	med	clay	0.11	3.81	2.27	0.97	clay	0.20	2.04	1.21	0.86	r90	1.38	2.11	1.51	0.87
ITA 1	r90	0.12	1.01	1.51	0.18	p90	clay	0.11	1.15	1.72	0.58	clay	0.11	1.17	1.75	0.50	r90	3.22	1.36	1.52	0.69
ITA 2	r90	0.09	1.29	1.63	0.61	p90	allTex	0.07	1.57	1.97	0.78	allTex	0.10	1.10	1.39	0.43	med	3.01	1.33	1.40	0.63
ITA 3	med	0.19	1.27	1.79	0.60	med	clay	0.15	1.55	2.19	0.76	allTex	0.18	1.30	1.84	0.60	r90	4.26	1.64	2.22	0.79
ITA 4	med	0.06	1.06	1.55	0.34	med	clay	0.06	1.06	1.56	0.34	allTex	0.07	0.97	1.42	-0.04	r90	1.67	1.04	1.48	0.31
ITA 5	med	0.16	1.20	1.55	0.49	med	allTex	0.16	1.20	1.55	0.49	allTex	0.17	1.13	1.46	0.39	med	3.04	1.99	2.34	0.86
TUR 1	r90	0.21	1.05	1.40	0.28	p90	clay	0.21	1.09	1.45	0.31	allTex	0.23	0.99	1.32	0.03	med	6.17	1.74	2.54	0.80
TUR 2	med	0.13	1.46	2.09	0.71	med	allTex	0.09	2.07	2.96	0.87	clay	0.11	1.71	2.45	0.80	r90	5.28	1.55	1.79	0.75
ESP 1	med	0.09	1.84	2.00	0.84	med	allTex	0.09	1.09	2.06	0.85	allTex	0.14	1.14	1.24	0.43	med	4.30	1.50	1.80	0.73
Median		0.21	1.26	1.55	0.58			0.20	1.46	1.75	0.71		0.21	1.13	1.40	0.42		2.94	1.39	1.70	0.70
Mean		0.28	1.37	1.55	0.53			0.26	1.53	1.73	0.63		0.33	1.20	1.40	0.38		2.94	1.48	1.92	0.60

348 ***Value of adding information on soil texture to the model***

349 The soil texture added to the satellite data as additional predictors in models for predicting SOC was
350 included as either clay or as information on all three particle size fractions, depending on which
351 combination of predictors resulted in the lowest RMSE. On average, combining satellite data and soil
352 texture data resulted in SOC prediction models with slightly but significantly higher RPD (mean
353 difference of 0.16; paired Wilcoxon, $p < 0.001$), RPIQ (mean difference of 0.18; $p < 0.001$), and ccc
354 (mean difference of 0.1; $p < 0.001$) values compared to using satellite data only (Table 1). There was a
355 weak but significant positive relationship between the benefit (difference in RPD) of adding soil texture
356 to the SOC prediction models and the strength of the absolute value of the Pearson correlation
357 coefficient $|r|$ between SOC and clay in soil (Pearson $r = 0.45$, $p < 0.01$). However, the variability
358 between the sites was large, and the prediction performance at several sites with a high correlation
359 between SOC and clay did not improve.

360

361 ***Influence of soil texture***

362 There was a significant positive correlation (Pearson $r = 0.42$, $p < 0.05$) between the performance (RPD)
363 of the models using satellite data and the absolute value of the Pearson correlation coefficient $|r|$
364 between SOC and clay in the soil. However, the correlation was weak, and for sites with a strong
365 correlation between SOC and clay content, both good and poor SOC models were found (Figure 6).
366 Examples of locations where the correlation between SOC and clay content seemed to be important
367 were the two Turkish sites. Both sites had large variations in clay content and fairly good prediction
368 models for clay. The variation in SOC was similar at the two sites, but only one of the sites (TUR 2) had
369 significant and strong correlations between SOC and clay content (TUR 1 $r = 0.00$, $p = 0.96$; TUR 2 $r =$
370 0.82 , $p < 0.001$), and it was at that site that SOC could be predicted considerably better (TUR 1 RPD
371 1.05; TUR 2 RPD 1.46). There was no statistical support for an overall correlation between SOC
372 prediction performance (RPD) from satellite data and the average amount (Pearson, $p = 0.51$ and 0.17)
373 or range ($p = 0.55$ and 0.36) of clay or SOC content, respectively. Similarly, there was no statistical

374 support for an overall correlation between the clay prediction performance (RPD) from satellite data
 375 and the average (Pearson, $p = 0.46$) and range ($p = 0.69$) of SOC. Neither did the clay prediction
 376 performance correlate with the average amount of clay content (Pearson, $p = 0.10$). However, there
 377 was a significant, but weak, correlation between the clay prediction performance and the range in clay
 378 content (Pearson $r = 0.48$, $p < 0.01$).

379
 380 *Figure 6.* RPD values of SOC prediction PLSR models using satellite data (median or R90, whichever gave the
 381 smaller RMSE for each site; corresponding to Table 1). The sites are sorted according to the RPD values and
 382 coloured according to the correlation between SOC and clay content at the sites (significant correlations at the
 383 0.05 level are indicated with an asterisk (*)).

384
 385 **Relative importance of satellite bands**

386 The relative importance of the satellite bands in the PLSR models for predicting SOC and clay content
 387 is presented in Figure 7 (and more detailed in Figure S3). The relative importance of the different bands
 388 varied largely between the models and sites. On average, across all sites, the visible range (especially
 389 the red to far-red wavelength range, B4 and B6) was more important in the SOC models compared
 390 with the clay models (paired Wilcoxon, $p < 0.05$), whereas the wavelength range around 2200 nm (B12)
 391 was more important in the clay models (paired Wilcoxon, $p < 0.05$).

392

393

394 *Figure 7.* Relative importance of predictors in PLSR models for predicting SOC and clay using satellite data
395 (median or R90, whichever resulted in the smallest RMSE for each site, corresponding to Table 1). Box plots with
396 lower and upper hinges representing 25th and 75th percentiles, line in between representing median, and
397 whiskers extending to 1.5 * IQR from both hinges. Jittered points represent individual sites. Shaded areas indicate
398 the bands with importance that are significantly different in SOC models compared to clay models (paired
399 Wilcoxon, 0.05 level). The dendrogram shows the redundancy structure of the set of predictors. It is based on a
400 (complete-linkage) hierarchical clustering of the median satellite dataset, with the distance between the bands
401 defined as $1 - |r|$ (Pearson).

402

403 Discussion

404 *Availability and quality of satellite data*

405 Using satellite images from several dates to find bare soil conditions is especially important when
406 developing regional models that include multiple fields with a mixture of spring and winter crops, as
407 well as differences in soil preparation and crop management. Although these conditions could be
408 expected to be similar within single fields, differences between satellite images from different dates

409 can be considerable and influence model performances, both for SOC (Vaudour *et al.*, 2019; Urbina-
410 Salazar *et al.*, 2021) and for clay (Gomez *et al.*, 2022), even for local models for single fields, such as in
411 this study. Using time series for individual fields to find the best possible or representative conditions
412 could therefore be advantageous. In the present study, using satellite data from 4 years (2019 to 2022),
413 however, resulted in less than on average 10 images per sampling point at 13 of the 34 sites, with 22
414 soil sampling points having as few as 3 (Figure 4A). A low number of satellite images could result in less
415 stable median and R90 data and thus less robust models when using these temporal mosaicking
416 approaches. However, there was no statistical support for a correlation between the performance of
417 the SOC and clay models and the number of available bare soil satellite images (Pearson $p = 0.68$ and
418 $p = 0.72$ for SOC and clay, respectively).

419 A possible drawback of the mosaic is that it might disrupt or attenuate otherwise continuous
420 patterns within the fields, as possibly observed from a single-date shot, such as short time variations
421 in soil moisture patterns. However, this did not seem to have been the case at the sites included in the
422 present study, where the temporal mosaics using both median and R90 showed continuous and very
423 similar spatial patterns (Figure S1 shows fields FRA 1, POL 1, and ESP 1). At the French site FRA 1, the
424 R90 enhanced the contrast between soils with different soil conditions compared with the median
425 mosaic, highlighting the differences between the parts of the field with calcareic Cambisols and the
426 Luvisols, and a recently moved field boundary. However, the R90 mosaic at the Polish site, POL 1, had
427 a small area showing inconsistencies in the general pattern and sharper differences between satellite
428 information from different dates. Although the small area in the Polish field did not include any of the
429 sampling points and therefore did not affect the models, similar artefacts on other sites might be part
430 of the explanation for the varying results when using R90.

431 The selected method for collecting satellite data aimed to find the best possible bare soil
432 conditions while using an automated procedure. The automated procedure made it easy to apply the
433 same methods and criteria to multiple sites, which is important for use on a larger scale or by non-
434 experts. However, the evident outliers at some of the sites using the R90 method despite the applied

435 filters (inset in Figure 4C) highlight the difficulties with addressing all disturbing factors and the
436 importance of validating the quality of the collected data.

437 ***Difficult predicting SOC and clay content from satellite data***

438 The prediction performance for SOC from satellite data of the 34 sites included in the study varied
439 largely, ranging from an RPD > 1.5 for 8 sites to as low as < 1.1 for another 8 sites (Table 1 and Figure
440 5). Similar variations in SOC prediction performance are also presented in a recent review when
441 considering SOC prediction models from satellite data without additional auxiliary variables (Vaudour
442 *et al.*, 2022). A relationship between soil texture and the satellite data was evident when comparing
443 the PCA score plot of the satellite data in Figure 4 with the texture triangle in Figure 3. However, it was
444 obvious that it did not explain all the variations in the satellite data. According to an RPIQ above or
445 equal to 1.7, half of the sites had acceptable models for clay, but only 10 of them also had an RPD
446 above 1.5 (Table 1 and Figure 5). The variable results in the present study correspond fairly well with
447 previously published results on clay predictions and classification that also include both poor and good
448 prediction models (e.g. Nanni *et al.*, 2006; Gomez *et al.*, 2018; Gomez *et al.*, 2019; Loiseau *et al.*, 2019).

449 Clay content is a mineral particle size fraction, whereas its spectrally active components are
450 related to clay and iron (hydr)oxide minerals, with different absorption patterns by different minerals
451 (Hunt & Salisbury, 1970). However, the narrow absorption features of different clay minerals cannot
452 be detected with a multispectral sensor. Potentially detectable differences in the absorption spectra
453 of the clay fraction could be related to differences in the proportions of clay minerals to iron
454 (hydr)oxides, which absorb in different parts of the spectra (Stenberg *et al.*, 2010). The models
455 presented in this study were developed for field and farm scale, where variation in mineralogy could
456 be expected to be small. However, differences in mineralogy might still be part of the explanation for
457 the varying results between sites; for example, carbonate was present at some of the sites but absent
458 at other sites.

459 Several soil spectroscopy studies have shown the benefit of geographically small-scale
460 calibration models due to the larger similarities in soil type and mineralogy (e.g. Kuang & Mouazen,
461 2011; Araújo *et al.*, 2014). However, the variation in the modelled soil property itself often explains
462 large parts of the differences seen in model performance (Stenberg *et al.*, 2010), and soil properties
463 can vary considerably within very short distances (Zhang & Hartemink, 2021). In the present study, the
464 ranges of observed values in clay content increased asymptotically with the area of the sites, but there
465 was no statistical support for a similar relationship for the ranges in SOC. In addition, there was no
466 statistical support for the prediction performance of SOC or clay models being related to the size of
467 the sites. A large variation in the soil properties to be predicted is often desired when developing
468 prediction models (Ramirez-Lopez *et al.*, 2014). A weak but significant correlation was observed
469 between the performance of the clay models and the ranges in clay content across the sites in this
470 study. The clay models at the Turkish sites TUR 1 and the Swedish site SWE 4 with the largest ranges
471 in clay content (both ~50%) were among the 30% best-performing models (RPD of 1.7 and 1.8; Figures
472 3B and 5, and Table 1). On the other hand, 4 of the 5 models with an RPD > 2 were at sites (CHE 5, CZE
473 2, FRA 1, SWE 5) with a medium range in clay content (10–30%). In contrast to the observation of the
474 clay models, there was no correlation between the ranges in SOC and model performance. However,
475 the three sites with the largest ranges in SOC content, SWE 1, DNK 2, and DNK 3, had SOC models with
476 RPD > 1.5 (Figures 3A and 5 and Table 1).

477 ***Influence of soil texture on SOC predictions***

478 A relationship of soil texture with the SOC predictions from satellite data was evident in the weak, but
479 significant, trend of increased SOC prediction performance with higher SOC to clay correlation in the
480 soils of the 34 sites. However, it was obvious that the positive relationships with soil texture could
481 explain only a small part of the large variation in SOC prediction performance across the sites. The
482 Danish sites DNK 1–3, for example, had comparably good SOC predictions but no significant correlation
483 between SOC and clay content (Figures 3D and 6). This might partly be explained by the high content

484 and large variation in SOC, combined with among the lowest content and variation in clay. This makes
485 variation in SOC the dominant soil property affecting water-holding capacity, and the main varying soil
486 property affecting the soil spectra at those sites. In cases where variation in SOC is more pronounced
487 than variation in texture, a strong correlation between SOC and clay content might instead help in clay
488 predictions. It might be difficult to identify whether one or the other of the two soil properties is
489 dominant, but the correlation between SOC and clay content might likely support models for both soil
490 properties, as may be the case at, for example, the Swiss sites CHE 2, 4, and 5 (Figures 3D and 6).

491 The influence of soil texture on the SOC predictions was also evident by the improvement in
492 the model performance when adding information on soil texture as predictors to the models, in
493 addition to the satellite data. However, this was not the case at all sites. Two examples with the largest
494 improvements were the Swiss site CHE 5 and the Turkish site TUR 2, where the SOC could be predicted
495 with RPD = 1.89 and 1.46, respectively, using only satellite data, and with RPD = 3.80 and 2.07 when
496 information on texture was used as an additional predictor (Table 1). The level of improvement when
497 including information on soil texture as an additional predictor was weakly correlated with the
498 absolute value of the correlation between SOC and clay content in soil. However, adding information
499 on soil texture to prediction models for SOC is not practical, as soil texture analyses are both time
500 consuming and expensive. Adding information on soil texture through available soil texture maps or
501 other sensor measurements, such as gamma ray measurements using proximal or remote sensing,
502 could be an alternative. In particular, ²³²Thorium concentration has been shown to be highly
503 correlated with clay content (Piikki & Söderström, 2019) and adding airborne gamma ray
504 measurements to a regional satellite-based model in central France improved SOC predictions (Urbina-
505 Salazar *et al.*, 2023).

506 Comparing the relative importance of the different satellite bands in the models for predicting
507 SOC to the importance in the models for predicting clay content revealed significant differences in two
508 spectral regions: For SOC, the bands in the red to far-red region of the visible spectrum (particularly

509 B4, B6) were more important than for clay, while the opposite was the case for the B12 band at around
510 2200 nm (Figure 7). Although the differences were significant, the variation between sites was large,
511 and the patterns were apparent only when considering the many sites in this study (Figures 7 and S3).
512 Nevertheless, the observed differences are consistent with what has been reported as important
513 spectral regions for SOC and clay predictions. Absorbance in the spectral region covered by Sentinel-2
514 B12, around 2200 nm, is a dominant feature of several common clay minerals (including Gibbsite, Illite,
515 Smectite, and Kaolinite; Stenberg *et al.*, 2010). Although organic matter also absorbs light in this
516 region, its absorbance is often reported to be weak. Evidence of the influence of organic matter in the
517 visible region is clear, and soil colour has been used to estimate SOC in a number of situations (e.g.
518 Gholizadeh *et al.*, 2020).

519 ***Large and variable set of study sites***

520 The large number of study sites with diverse pedo-climatic conditions from across Europe captured in
521 this study made it possible to assess general patterns between field- and farm-scale models related to
522 variations in SOC and soil texture. However, this diversity could also present challenges, as a wide
523 range of conditions may have masked correlations between model performance and the SOC and soil
524 texture relationship. Differences in SOC and clay content were discussed earlier in this paper and are
525 indicative of differences in soil type. However, available data on dominant soil types (Supplementary
526 Table S1), diagnostic horizons of topsoils, and other related soil properties did not allow for a more
527 thorough investigation.

528 There was no evidence of especially poor results at sites with a long time between soil
529 sampling and the collection of satellite data. There was also no statistical support for a relationship
530 between model performance and the number of samples (Pearson $p = 0.42$ and $p = 0.97$ for SOC and
531 clay) and no or weak statistical support for a relationship between model performance and the sample
532 density ($p = 0.37$ and $p = 0.06$, $r = -0.33$, for SOC and clay). Another difference between the sites in
533 relation to the soil sampling was the differences in the areas that the individual soil samples

534 represented. At several of the sites, the sampling was not designed for satellite modelling applications,
535 with sampling points unadjusted to the satellite pixels in terms of location inside the pixel or in terms
536 of the size of the area sampled for each point. Sampling points from a very small area might, for
537 example, lead to low representability of the 100 m² or 400 m² satellite pixels. However, some of the
538 best models were developed at sites where the individual soil sampling point represented only 0.25
539 m² (CHE 2, 4, and 5), and no general patterns could be observed related to the area represented by a
540 soil sample.

541

542 **Conclusion**

543 This study investigated the influence of soil texture on SOC predictions from Sentinel-2 data with an
544 unprecedented set of 34 local-scale study areas across 10 European countries. The prediction
545 performance for both SOC and clay content varied largely between the sites when only satellite data
546 was used as predictors, with RPD values ranging from around 1 to 3.2 and RPD values > 1.5 observed
547 at 8 and 12 of the 34 sites for SOC and clay, respectively.

548 In response to the research questions, we draw the following conclusions:

- 549 1) There was statistical support for better SOC prediction performance at sites with a stronger
550 correlation between SOC and clay content in the soil. However, these relationships could
551 explain only a small part of the overall variation in SOC model performances across the sites.
- 552 2) Differences in the range and overall amount of clay content between the sites could not
553 explain the variation in SOC prediction performance.
- 554 3) Adding information on soil texture as additional predictors to the models improved the SOC
555 prediction on average, but, as with the modelling results, the added value varied largely
556 between the sites.
- 557 4) The relative importance of the different spectral bands in the SOC and clay models indicated
558 that the models for the two soil properties used different information in the satellite data to

559 some degree, with the red and far-red regions of the visible spectrum more important for SOC
560 prediction and the region around 2200 nm more important for clay prediction.

561 The influence of soil texture on SOC prediction performance, although weak and variable across all
562 studied sites, emphasises the need for caution when interpreting SOC predictions from satellite data.
563 This could explain some of the difficulties in expanding models to cover larger areas and might lead to
564 problems with relying only on satellite data for monitoring changes in SOC over time.

565

566 **Acknowledgements**

567 The authors thank the local support teams taking the field data, and Tereza Zádorová for help with the
568 soil classification. This study was produced within the activities of the STEROPES project
569 (<https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/STEROPES>), of the EJP SOIL funded by the European Union's Horizon
570 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862695.

571

572 **References**

573 Angelopoulou, T., Tziolas, N., Balafoutis, A., Zalidis, G. & Bochtis, D. 2019. Remote sensing techniques
574 for soil organic carbon estimation: A review. *Remote Sensing*, **11**, 676.
575 <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11060676>

576 Araújo, S.R., Wetterlind, J., Demattê, J.A.M. & Stenberg, B. 2014. Improving the prediction
577 performance of a large tropical vis-NIR spectroscopic soil library from Brazil by clustering into
578 smaller subsets or use of data mining calibration techniques. *European Journal of Soil Sciences*,
579 **65**, 718–729. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12165>

580 Aybar, C., Wu, Q., Bautista, L., Yali R. & Barja, A. 2020. rgee: An R package for interacting with Google
581 *Earth Engine Journal of Open Source Software*, <https://github.com/r-spatial/rgee/>.

582 Bablet, A., Vu, P.V.H., Jacquemoud, S., Viallefont-Robinet, F., Fabre, S., Briottet, X. *et al.* 2018. MARMIT:
583 A multilayer radiative transfer model of soil reflectance to estimate surface soil moisture content
584 in the solar domain (400–2500 nm). *Remote Sensing of Environment*, **217**, 1–17.
585 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.07.031>

586 Balesdent, J., Chenu, C. & Balabane, M. 2000, Relationship of soil organic matter dynamics to physical
587 protection and tillage. *Soil and Tillage Research*, **53**, 215-230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167->
588 [1987\(99\)00107-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(99)00107-5).

589 Barthès, B.G. & Chotte, J. 2021. Infrared spectroscopy approaches support soil organic carbon
590 estimations to evaluate land degradation. *Land Degrad Dev*, **32**, 310–322.
591 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.3718>

592 Bartholomeus, H., Kooistra, L., Stevens, A., Van Leeuwen, M., Van Wesemael, B., Ben-Dor, E. *et al.*
593 2011. Soil organic carbon mapping of partially vegetated agricultural fields with imaging
594 spectroscopy. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, **13**, 81–88.
595 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2010.06.009>

596 Bousbih, S., Zribi, M., Pelletier, C., Gorrab, A., Lili-Chabaane, Z., Baghdadi, N. *et al.* 2019. Soil texture
597 Estimation using radar and optical data from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2. *Remote Sens*, **11**, 1520.
598 <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11131520>

599 Castaldi, F., Palombo, A., Pascucci, S., Pignatti, S., Santini F. & Casa, R. 2015. Reducing the influence of
600 soil moisture on the estimation of clay from hyperspectral data: A case study using simulated
601 PRISMA data. *Remote Sensing*, **7**, 15561–15582. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs71115561>

602 Castaldi, F., Chabrilat, S., Don, A. & van Wesemael, B. 2019b. Soil organic carbon mapping using LUCAS
603 topsoil database and Sentinel-2 Data: An approach to reduce soil moisture and crop residue
604 effects. *Remote Sensing*, **11**, 18, 2121. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11182121>

605 Castaldi, F. 2021. Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 multi-temporal series to estimate topsoil properties on
606 cropland. *Remote Sensing*, **13**, 3345. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13173345>

607 Castaldi, F., Koparan, M.H., Wetterlind, J., Žydelis, R., Vinci, I., Savaş, A.Ö. *et al.* 2023. Assessing the
608 capability of Sentinel-2 time-series to estimate soil organic carbon and clay content at local scale
609 in croplands. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, **199**, 40–60,
610 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2023.03.016>

611 Demattê, J.A.M., Fongaro, C.T., Rizzo, R. & Safanelli, J.L. 2018. Geospatial Soil Sensing System (GEOS3):
612 A powerful data mining procedure to retrieve soil spectral reflectance from satellite images.
613 *Remote Sensing of Environment*, **212**, 161–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.04.047>

614 Dvorakova, K., Shi, P., Limbourg, Q. & Van Wesemael, B. 2020. Soil organic carbon mapping from
615 remote sensing: The effect of crop residues. *Remote Sensing*, **12**, 1913.
616 <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12121913>

617 Filzmoser, P., Hron, K. & Templ, M. 2018. *Applied Compositional Data Analysis*. Cham: Springer.
618 <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-96422-5>

619 Gholizadeh, A., Žižala, D., Saberioon, M. & Borůvka, L. 2018. Soil organic carbon and texture retrieving
620 and mapping using proximal, airborne and Sentinel-2 spectral imaging. *Remote Sensing of*
621 *Environment*, **218**, 89–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.09.015>

622 Gholizadeh, A., Saberioon, M., Viscarra Rossel, R.A., Boruvka, L. & Klement, A. 2020. Spectroscopic
623 measurements and imaging of soil colour for field scale estimation of soil organic carbon.
624 *Geoderma*, **357**, 113972. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.113972>.

625 Gomez, C., Vaudour, E., Féret, J.-B., De Boissieu, F. & Dharumarajan, S. 2022. Topsoil clay content
626 mapping in croplands from Sentinel-2 data: Influence of atmospheric correction methods across
627 a season time series. *Geoderma*, **423**, 115959. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2022.115959>

628 Gomez, C., Dharumarajan, S., Féret, J.-B., Lagacherie, P., Ruiz, L. & Sekhar, M. 2019. Use of Sentinel-2
629 time-series images for classification and uncertainty analysis of inherent biophysical property:
630 Case of soil texture mapping. *Remote Sensing*, **11**, 565. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11050565>

631 Gomez, C., Adeline, K., Bacha, S., Driessen, B., Gorretta, N., Lagacherie, P. *et al.* 2018. Sensitivity of clay
632 content prediction to spectral configuration of VNIR/SWIR imaging data, from multispectral to
633 hyperspectral scenarios. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, **204**, 18–30,
634 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2017.10.047>

635 Gorelick, N., Hancher, M., Dixon, M., Ilyushchenko, S., Thau, D. & Moore, R. 2017. Google Earth Engine:
636 Planetary-scale geospatial analysis for everyone. *Remote sensing of Environment*, **202**, 18–27.

637 Gras, J.-P., Barthès, B.G., Mahaut, B. & Trupin, S. 2014. Best practices for obtaining and processing field
638 visible and near infrared (VNIR) spectra of topsoils. *Geoderma*, **214–215**, 126–134.
639 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2013.09.021>

640 Heiden, U., d'Angelo, P., Schwind, P., Karlshöfer, P., Müller, R., Zepp, S. *et al.* 2022. Soil reflectance
641 composites—Improved thresholding and performance evaluation. *Remote Sensing*, **14**, 4526.
642 <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14184526>

643 Hunt, G.R. & Salisbury, J.W. 1970. Visible and near-infrared spectra of minerals and rocks: I. Silicate
644 minerals. *Modern Geology*, **1**, 283–300.

645 Khosravi, V., Gholizadeh, A., Žižala, D., Kodešová, R., Saberioon, M., Agyeman, P.C. *et al.* 2024. On the
646 impact of soil texture on local scale organic carbon quantification: From airborne to spaceborne
647 sensing domains. *Soil and Tillage Research*, **241**, 106125.
648 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2024.106125>

649 Knadel, M., Castaldi, F., Barbetti, R., Ben-Dor, E., Gholizadeh, A., & Lorenzetti, R. 2022. Mathematical
650 techniques to remove moisture effects from visible–near-infrared–shortwave-infrared soil
651 spectra—Review. *Applied Spectroscopy Reviews*, **58**, 629–662.
652 <https://doi.org/10.1080/05704928.2022.2128365>

653 Kuang, B. & Mouazen, A. M. 2011. Calibration of visible and near infrared spectroscopy for soil analysis
654 at the field scale on three European farms. *European Journal of Soil Science*, **62**, 629–636.

655 Loiseau, T., Chen, S., Mulder, V.L., Román Dobarco, M., Richer-de-Forges, A.C. *et al.* 2019. Satellite data
656 integration for soil clay content modelling at a national scale. *International Journal of Applied*
657 *Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, **82**, 101905. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2019.101905>

658 Loveland, P. & Webb, J. 2003. Is there a critical level of organic matter in the agricultural soils of
659 temperate regions: A review. *Soil and Tillage Research*, **70**, 1–18. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(02)00139-3)
660 [1987\(02\)00139-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(02)00139-3)

661 Lundberg, S. M., Lee, S. I. 2017. A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. Advances in
662 neural information processing systems. 31st Conference on Neural Information Processing
663 Systems (NIPS 2017), Long Beach, CA, USA.

664 Manns, H.R., Parkin, G.W. & Martin, R.C. 2016. Evidence of a union between organic carbon and water
665 content in soil. *Can. J. Soil. Sci.* **96**, 305–316. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjss-2015-0084>

666 Metzger, M.J., Bunce, R.G.H, Jongman, R.H.G, Múcher, C.A. & Watkins, J.W. 2005. A climatic
667 stratification of the environment of Europe. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, **14**, 549–563. DOI
668 link: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822x.2005.00190.x>

669 Metzger, K., Liebisch, F., Herrera J.M., Guillaume, T. & Bragazza, L. 2024. Prediction accuracy of soil
670 chemical parameters by field- and laboratory-obtained vis-NIR spectra after external parameter
671 orthogonalization. *Sensors*, **24**, 3556. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24113556>

672 Minasny, B., McBratney, A.B., Bellon-Maurel, V., Roger, J.-M., Gobrecht, A., Ferrand, L. *et al.* 2011.
673 Removing the effect of soil moisture from NIR diffuse reflectance spectra for the prediction of soil
674 organic carbon. *Geoderma*, **167–168**, 118–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2011.09.008>

675 Mzid N, Castaldi, F., Tolomio, M., Pascucci, S., Casa, R. & Pignatti, S. 2013. Evaluation of agricultural
676 bare soil properties retrieval from Landsat 8, Sentinel-2 and PRISMA satellite data. *Remote*
677 *Sensing*, **14**, 714. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14030714>

678 Nanni, M.R. & Demattê, J.A.M. 2006. Spectral reflectance methodology in comparison to traditional
679 soil analysis. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, **70**, 393–407. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2003.0285>

680 Nemes A., Wösten J.H.M., Lilly A. & Oude Voshaar J.H. 1999. Evaluation of different procedures to
681 interpolate particle-size distributions to achieve compatibility within soil databases. *Geoderma*,
682 **90**, 187–202. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(99\)00014-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(99)00014-2)

683 Nocita, M., Stevens, A., Noon, C. & Van Wesemael, B. 2013. Prediction of soil organic carbon for
684 different levels of soil moisture using Vis-NIR spectroscopy. *Geoderma*, **199**, 37–42.
685 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2012.07.020>

686 Ogen, Y., Neumann, C., Chabrilat, S., Goldshleger, N. & Ben Dor, E. 2018. Evaluating the detection limit
687 of organic matter using point and imaging spectroscopy. *Geoderma*, **321**, 100–109.
688 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.02.011>

689 Ouerghemmi, W., Gomez, C., Naceur, S., Lagacherie, P. 2016. Semi-blind source separation for the
690 estimation of the clay content over semi-vegetated areas using VNIR/SWIR hyperspectral airborne
691 data. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, **181**, 251–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2016.04.013>

692 Pandey, P.C. & Pandey, M. 2023. Highlighting the role of agriculture and geospatial technology in food
693 security and sustainable development goals. *Sustainable Development*, **31**, 3175–3195.
694 <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2600>

695 Pedregosa, F., Varoquaux, G., Gramfort, A., Michel, V., Thirion, B., Grisel, O. *et al.* 2011. Scikit-learn:
696 Machine learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, **12**, 2825–2830.

697 Piccini, C., Metzger, K., Debaene, G., Stenberg, B., Götzinger, S., Borůvka, L. *et al.* 2024. In-field soil
698 spectroscopy in Vis–NIR range for fast and reliable soil analysis: A review. *European J Soil Science*,
699 **75**, e13481. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13481>

700 Piikki, K. & Söderström, M. 2019. Digital soil mapping of arable land in Sweden – Validation of
701 performance at multiple scales, *Geoderma*, **352**, 342–350.
702 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.10.049>

703 Piikki, K., Wetterlind, J., Söderström, M. & Stenberg, B. (2021). Perspectives on validation in digital soil
704 mapping of continuous attributes—A review. *Soil Use and Management*, **37**, 7–21.

705 R Core Team. 2024. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for
706 Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org>

707 Ramirez-Lopez, L., Schmidt, K., Behrens, T., van Wesemael, B., Demattê, J.A.M. & Scholten, T. 2014.
708 Sampling optimal calibration sets in soil infrared spectroscopy. *Geoderma*, **226–227**, 140–150.
709 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2014.02.002>

710 SENTINEL-2 User Handbook. 2015. <https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/247904/685211/Sentinel->
711 [2 User Handbook](https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/247904/685211/Sentinel-2_User_Handbook)

712 Smith, P., Soussana, J., Angers, D., Schipper, L., Chenu, C., Rasse, D.P. *et al.* 2020. How to measure,
713 report and verify soil carbon change to realize the potential of soil carbon sequestration for
714 atmospheric greenhouse gas removal. *Global Change Biology*, **26**, 219–241.
715 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14815>

716 Soltani, I., Fouad, Y., Michot, D., Bréger, P., Dubois, R. & Cudennec, C. 2019. A near infrared index to
717 assess effects of soil texture and organic carbon content on soil water content. *European J Soil*
718 *Science*, **70**, 151–161. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12725>

719 Soubry, I., Doan, T., Chu, T. & Guo, X. 2021. A systematic review on the integration of remote sensing
720 and GIS to forest and grassland ecosystem health attributes, indicators, and measures. *Remote*
721 *Sensing*, **13**, 3262. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13163262>

722 Stenberg, B. 2010. Effects of soil sample pretreatments and standardised rewetting as interacted with
723 sand classes on Vis-NIR predictions of clay and soil organic carbon. *Geoderma*, **158**, 15–22,
724 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2010.04.008>.

725 Stenberg, B., Viscarra Rossel, R.A., Mouazen, A.M. & Wetterlind, J. 2010. Chapter Five - Visible and
726 near infrared spectroscopy in soil science. *In: Advances in Agronomy* (ed. D.L. Sparks), pp. 163–
727 215. Academic Press. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113\(10\)07005-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113(10)07005-7)

728 Urbina-Salazar, D., Vaudour, E., Baghdadi, N., Ceschia, E., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Lehmann, S. *et al.*
729 2021. Using Sentinel-2 images for soil organic carbon content mapping in croplands of
730 southwestern France. the usefulness of Sentinel-1/2 derived moisture maps and mismatches
731 between Sentinel images and sampling dates. *Remote Sensing*, **13**, 5115.
732 <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13245115>

733 Urbina-Salazar, D., Vaudour, E., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Chen, S., Martelet, G., Baghdadi, N. *et al.* 2023.
734 Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1 bare soil temporal mosaics of 6-year periods for soil organic carbon
735 content mapping in Central France. *Remote Sensing*, **15**, 2410.
736 <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15092410>

737 Vaudour, E., Gholizadeh, A., Castaldi, F., Saberioon, M.; Borůvka, L., Urbina-Salazar, D. *et al.* 2022.
738 Satellite imagery to map topsoil organic carbon content over cultivated areas: An overview.
739 *Remote Sens.*, **14**, 2917. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14122917>

740 Vaudour, E., Gomez, C., Loiseau, T., Baghdadi, N., Loubet, B., Arrouays, D. *et al.* 2019. The impact of
741 acquisition date on the prediction performance of topsoil organic carbon from Sentinel-2 for
742 croplands. **Remote Sensing**, **11**, 2143. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11182143>

743 Wang, J., Zhen, J., Hu, W., Chen, S., Lizaga, I., Zeraatpisheh, M. & Yang, X. 2023. Remote sensing of soil
744 degradation: Progress and perspective. *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, **11**,
745 429–454. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iswcr.2023.03.002>

746 Wetterlind, J., Piikki, K., Söderström, M. & Stenberg, B. 2015. Exploring the predictability of soil texture
747 and organic matter content with a commercial integrated soil profiling tool. *European Journal of*
748 *Soil Science*, **66**, 631-638

749 Viscarra Rossel, R.A., Cattle, S.R., Ortega, A. & Fouad, Y. 2009. In situ measurements of soil colour,
750 mineral composition and clay content by vis–NIR spectroscopy. *Geoderma*, **150**, 253–266.
751 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2009.01.025>

752 Viscarra Rossel, R.A., Walvoort, D.J.J., McBratney, A.B., Janik, L.J. & Skjemstad, J.O. 2006. Visible, near
753 infrared, mid infrared or combined diffuse reflectance spectroscopy for simultaneous assessment
754 of various soil properties. *Geoderma*, **131**, 59–75.
755 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2005.03.007>

756 Wight, J.P., Ashworth, A.J. & Allen, F.L. 2016. Organic substrate, clay type, texture, and water influence
757 on NIR carbon measurements. *Geoderma*, **261**, 36–43.
758 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.06.021>

759 Wösten J.H.M, Lilly A., Nemes A., Le Bas C. 1999. Development and use of a database of hydraulic
760 properties of European soils. *Geoderma*, **90**, 169–185. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(98)00132-3)
761 [7061\(98\)00132-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(98)00132-3)

762 Yuzugullu, O., Fajraoui, N., Don, A. & Liebisch, F. 2024. Satellite-based soil organic carbon mapping on
763 European soils using available datasets and support sampling. *Science of Remote Sensing*, **9**,
764 100118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.srs.2024.100118>

765 Zhang, Y. & Hartemink, A.E. 2021. Quantifying short-range variation of soil texture and total carbon of
766 a 330-ha farm. *Catena*, **201**, 105200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2021.105200>.

767 Zayani, H., Fouad, Y., Michot, D., Kassouk, Z., Baghdadi, N., Vaudour, E. *et al.* 2023. Using machine-
768 learning algorithms to predict soil organic carbon content from combined remote sensing imagery
769 and laboratory Vis-NIR spectral datasets. *Remote Sensing*, **15**, 4264.
770 <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15174264>

771 Žížala, D., Minařík, R., Skála, J., Beitlerová, H., Juřicová, A., Reyes Rojas, J. *et al.* 2022. High-resolution
772 agriculture soil property maps from digital soil mapping methods, Czech Republic. *Catena*, **212**,
773 106024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2022.106024>